

Organic Pesticides. Part VI. Synthesis of Certain Fluorophenols and their Allyl Ethers

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For studying pesticidal activity of organic fluorine compounds, six fluorophenols have been prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of the corresponding fluorohydroxyketones, reported earlier. All of them have been converted into their allyl ethers. These twelve compounds have been evaluated for their insecticidal activity with adult house flies (*Musea domestica*) as the test insect.

Phenols have wide antimicrobial activity and the halogen atom and the alkyl groups, when attached to the aromatic nucleus, enhance greatly this toxicity (Gruenhagen *et al.*, Contributions from Boyce Thomson Institute, 1951, **16**, 349). Very little work appears to have been done on arylphenols containing fluorine (Kindler *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1953, **86**, 501; 1954, **87**, 194). We have now prepared six fluoro-alkyl and-aryl substituted phenols as potential pesticides by the Clemmensen reduction of certain fluorohydroxyketones reported earlier (Joshi and Bahel, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 687).

Further, phenolic ethers have also been investigated as pesticides (Felton and McLaughlin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, **12**, 298). The validity of the hypothesis that a good contact insecticide must have a combination of a toxic and lipoid-soluble groupings in its molecule (Langer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, **27**, 918) was justified by Langer *et al.* who also showed that allyloxy-aryl ethers possessed a marked toxicity. We have therefore converted the above fluorophenols into their allyl ethers so that the compounds contain both a neurotoxic halo-aryl group and an ether linkage having lipophilic property.

The insecticidal activity of these compounds has been evaluated against adult house flies (*Musea domestica*) and some of them have been found to be fairly active.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorohydroxyketones were prepared by the method reported in an earlier communication (*loc. cit.*). Fluorophenols were obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the above hydroxyketones.

Amalgamated zinc was prepared by shaking for 15 minutes a mixture of zinc (20 g.), mercuric chloride (20 g.), HCl (conc., 20 c.c.), and water (10 c. c.), decanting, and finally washing the residue with water. It was refluxed with ethanol (30 c.c.), HCl (conc., 10 c.c.), and the fluorohydroxyketone (0.02M) for 10 to 12 hours, during which 2 c. c. portion of HCl (conc.) was added after every hour. At the end of this period a drop of the liquid failed to give any colour with aqueous ferric chloride solution. After removal of ethanol the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with 2%

TABLE I
Fluorophenols.

*S. No.	Hydroxyfluoroketones.	Alkyl or aryl fluorophenols.	Yield.	B.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	R- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-K	2-(<i>o</i> -Chloro-)-benzyl-Fp	41.7%	245°/10 mm	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ OClF	65.56	65.53	4.23	4.30
2.	R- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-K	2-(<i>p</i> -fluoro)-benzyl-Fp	95.8	270°/15	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ OF ₂	70.63	70.90	4.34	4.54
3.	R- <i>m</i> -tolyl-K	2-(<i>m</i> -Methyl)-benzyl-Fp	83.4	**260°/3	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ OF	77.55	77.77	5.84	6.01
4.	R- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-K	2-(<i>p</i> -Methoxy)-benzyl-Fp	88.7	185°/7	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ F	72.12	72.41	5.55	5.80
5.	R-Heptylo-K	2-Octyl ⁿ -Fp	73.0	200°/30	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ OF	74.76	75.00	9.23	9.39
6.	R-styryl-K	2-(1'-Phenyl)-propenyl-Fp	83.5	235°/16	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ OF	79.05	79.44	5.74	5.70

** These index-numbers have been used in Table III.

** Melts completely at 165°.

R = 1-hydroxy-4-fluorophenyl.

K = ketone (2-acyl).

Fp = 4-fluorophenol.

TABLE II

** *Alkyl (alkyl or aryl) ethers.*

*S. N.	Allyl-Ethers	Yield.	B.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
7.	A-2(<i>o</i> -chloro-)benzyl-Fb	42.5%	190°/2mm	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ OClF	69.76	69.43	5.20	5.08
8.	A-2(<i>p</i> -fluoro-)benzyl-Fb	63.5	185°/30	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ OF ₂	73.61	73.84	5.20	5.38
9.	A-2(<i>m</i> -methyl)-benzyl-Fb	67.7	200°/2	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ OF	79.92	79.25	6.34	6.64
10.	A-2(<i>p</i> -methoxy)-benzyl-Fb	85.1	140°/4	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ F	74.69	75.00	6.38	6.25
11.	A-2-octyl ⁿ -Fb	84.6	150°/2	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ OF	78.98	77.27	9.21	9.41
12.	A-2(1'-phenyl)propenyl-Fb	68.2	170°/2	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ OF	69.09	80.59	6.21	6.34

** Six Fluorophenols used are the same as in Table I.

** These index-numbers have been used in Table III.

A = 1-allyloxy.

Fb = 4-fluorobenzene.

sodium carbonate solution and water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride; the ether was removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. The compounds are listed in Table I.

Allyl Ethers.—These were prepared by the method reported earlier (*loc. cit.*) by treating the phenol (0.1 *M*) with allyl bromide (0.11 *M*) and freshly fused potassium carbonate (0.15 *M*) in dry acetone (100 c. c.) medium. The allyl ethers obtained are listed in Table II.

Evaluation of Insecticidal Activity.—The insecticidal activity was evaluated against adult house flies (*Musca domestica*) as the test insect. The compounds were dissolved in acetone and later diluted in kerosine oil. The samples were first tested at a concentration of 1%, adopting the usual glass plate petri dish method. The results of these tests, however, did not prove quite successful as the mean mortality did not reach 100% even at the end of 24 hours of exposure. Subsequent trials, using the various materials as space sprays in specially constructed metallic chambers, also proved inconclusive. Finally, the technique of applying the products at high concentration on the basis of mg. of active ingredient per square foot on glass slabs was again adopted. The results of these tests are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Formulation.	Dosage. (mg./ft. ² .)	Replications.	Mean K. D. time.	
			50% (M.S.)	100% (H.M.S.)
Sample No. 1	201.60	10	28.04	1.18.00
Sample No. 2	232.65	10	58.07	Overnight
Sample No. 3	225.90	10	11.47	"
Sample No. 4	166.95	7	3.22	6.44
Sample No. 5	45.00	10	11.33	19.32
Sample No. 6	208.80	10	14.58	34.18
Sample No. 7	193.50	10	19.30	36.04
Sample No. 8	164.25	10	40.20	26.03
Sample No. 9	45.00	10	3.50	5.20
Sample No. 10	45.00	10	3.08	5.27
Sample No. 11	45.00	10	10.17	13.31
Sample No. 12	190.00	10	26.00	43.56

The samples No. 4, 9, and 10 have been found to be most promising, whereas others are mildly effective as insecticides. The samples may prove insecticidally efficient for a different range of insects, but due to limited facilities at our disposal, these could not be investigated over a greater spectrum.

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